

Mazu Festival of Meizhou Island: The Construction and Interaction of Social Network of Chinese People in Modern Society

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Abstract

Mazu Festival has a long history, it is rich in social, cultural and artistic value. It is an important part and manifestation of Mazu belief. During the ceremony of Mazu Festival, some important nodes such as Mazu folk organizations, official organizations, local people, believers, tourists, and spectators, which have formed an intertwined and closely linked social network centered on Mazu belief. They are setting connection and are interactive through the ceremony. For these participants, it is of great significance to be able to personally experience and get in touch with Mazu closely. This has also greatly promoted the spread and development of Mazu culture. This article studies and analyzes the social network in the Mazu Festival, to clarify the important significance and role of the inheritance and development of Mazu Festival in modern society.

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Introduction

Mazu Festival is an important activity for modern people to worship Mazu. The full name is a large-scale ceremony to worship Mazu, which originated from traditional Mazu sacrifice rituals and folklore activities, with a long history and far-reaching influence. Mazu Festival is an important part and essence of Mazu belief. In 2006, Mazu belief was included in “The List of National Intangible Cultural Heritage”. In 2009, Mazu belief was included in “The List of Representatives of Human Intangible Cultural Heritage” by UNESCO, becoming China’s first human intangible cultural heritage in belief category. It marks that Mazu culture has risen from an important part of the excellent traditional culture of the Chinese nation to the height of the world, becoming the common wealth of all mankind.

The ceremony of Mazu Festival is a stage for individual social actors to perform, as well as a stage for social interaction, and a presentation of the social network of Mazu. Each role participating in the ceremony can realize true self-identity, recognize their position in the social structure, fulfill their respective obligations, and give play to their due role relationships. The ceremony of Mazu Festival embodies the organizational norms, the role of the organization, compliance with the rules and other aspects, which are orderly and integrated. Through the folklore performance of Mazu, Mazu culture has been fully integrated into the local culture and people’s lives.

We can explore the role of the ceremony of Mazu Festival in the construction of the social network through the Mazu organizations, ceremony, participants, and community interaction in the ceremony of Mazu Festival.

1.1 Mazu organizations

The theme of the Spring Festival Ceremony to commemorate the 1060th anniversary of Mazu’s birth in 2020 is that Chinese national people fight the ‘epidemic’ together, Meizhou Mazu blesses the common people. The ceremonial activities are organized by the Board of Directors of Meizhou Mazu Ancestral Temple as the organizer and sponsor of the ceremony of Mazu Festival, and they are guided by the Chinese Mazu Cultural Exchange Association and the Management Committee of the Meizhou Island Party Working Committee.

Figure 1: The ceremony of Mazu Festival in 2020

Source: Screenshot of video, taken by Ke Yihan, 2020

The Board of Directors of Meizhou Mazu ancestral temple is at the core of Mazu belief, it is responsible for the overall coordination of activities and the implementation of the ceremony activities, including arrangements of volunteers, various information announced to the outside world, the organization and planning of activities, the report of activities and other large and small matters. During major festivals, the members of the board of directors are very busy making the events to be completed smoothly.

As the highest level of national social organization, the Chinese Mazu Cultural Exchange Association occupies the core and key position in the Mazu social network. It plays an important function and role in organizing event participants, contacting the masses of Mazu believers, enterprises, and social groups at home and abroad. The association uses its own platform advantages, with the help of the power of the country and the media to give full play to the bond of Mazu belief, to bring together the Chinese people who believe in Mazu at home and abroad. The Chinese Mazu Cultural Exchange Association increase contact and exchanges for the Chinese people who miss their hometown and love the motherland. Before Mazu's major festivals, the majority of Mazu believers, caring enterprises, and Mazu civil organizations will actively contact the association to express their desires to participate in activities and give love. The association can also release event information and contact information promptly, so that people can have the opportunity to participate in the event, return to the motherland, or get closer to the belief center of Mazu, and can also contribute their own strength.

As the main body of the government, the Management Committee of the Party Working Committee of Meizhou Island is a government department directly managing Meizhou Island. As a supervisory and guiding department, it has played an important role in playing the government's resource advantages, power output, coordinating the relationship between the board of directors and relevant government departments at all levels and the development of work. Although Mazu belief itself has a unique advantage of emotional support, and people are willing to serve Mazu and facilitate various activities of Mazu, but it will be easier to coordinate many affairs or official work with the official background.

These related Mazu organizations play an important role in the activities of Mazu Festival, they are important nodes in the social network of Mazu belief, which play a key role as a link, and build a good communication platform for connecting Mazu and the public.

1.2 The connections in the ceremony of Mazu Festival

The ceremony of Mazu Festival refers to various procedures in the ceremony, including shaking divination sticks, hand washing, kneeling, offering incense, 'Sanxianli', burning silk, and burning the first incense. Social anthropologist Victor Turner believes that these sacrificial rituals can bring personal feelings of detachment, comfort, safety, and even ecstasy, or a sense of intimacy for the people who participate in the rituals together. The purpose of sacrificial rituals is to help people to pass some hurdles more easily in their lives, such as birth, old age, sickness and death.

Sacrificial offerings mainly reflect the communication between humans and gods, the sacrificial ritual is based on the exchanges between humans and gods, and adds more aspects of communication between people. Sacrificial ritual, as a symbolic sign, promotes the interaction between people and society or community, which in turn generates cultural identity.

On March 23rd of the lunar calendar in 2020, the ceremony to commemorate the 1060th anniversary of Mazu's birth was grandly held in Meizhou Island. Lin Jinzan, the Chairman of the Board of Directors of Meizhou Mazu ancestral temple, served as the chief worshiper and represented the majority of believers in front of the Mazu altar and did a series of ceremonies of Mazu Festival, such as reading the sacrificial text, offering the incense, kneeling, offering rituals, burning silk and burning the sacrificial text, he was sincere and respectful

to Mazu. This kind of ceremony is a collective memory that exists in the hearts of all believers. In the ceremony, it is used as a symbol, which contains a deeper meaning and symbolizes people's understanding and awe of Mazu belief.

At the same time and space, people participating in sacrificial rituals have similar or common perceptions of themselves and the world, so they have a cultural identity with each other, at the same time, after discovering self and determining self, they form self-identity. Due to the performance and repetitive nature of the ritual, the ritual itself is inherited over time and space, and the worldview symbolized by this ritual can be passed down to later generations in the form of collective memory. People also realize exchanges and cultural inheritance with the help of symbolic signs of sacrificial rituals. In such a process of creating, sharing, correcting and preserving reality, the realization of self-identity established based on Mazu belief by individuals has been strengthened, and it has provided a powerful force for reshaping the common culture of ethnic groups and provide strong support for forming stable group relations.

In recent years, the ceremony items of "the first incense" have been added to the ceremonies of Mazu Festival. Before the ceremony of Mazu Festival, the Board of Directors of Meizhou Mazu ancestral temple will receive donations from Chinese and overseas Chinese all the world, local private entrepreneurs or villagers, or know their donation intentions, and then, during the ceremony, these donors or their representatives will be arranged to worship Mazu in front of the Mazu altar under the leadership of the chairman, while other believers can only worship Mazu under the Mazu altar. In such a ceremony, if we regard the donation of 'the first incense' as a kind of sacrificial offering, then the symbolic meaning is that the person who offers "the first incense" is praying for Mazu to approve that his property has a sacred origin. The subordination relationship between humans and gods is the root of this legitimacy. The donors of 'the first incense' formally expressed their recognition of the subordination relationship through this ceremony to obtain the legitimacy of the property in the current life and the possibility of property in the future. The donors regard 'the first incense' as an honor and a sense of pride in their self-identity. They dedicate money to Mazu, pass on the sincerity and message of respect to Mazu, realize dialogue with Mazu through the intermediary of money, and look forward to receiving Mazu's protection. They are often the most devout believers. They recognize their identity as Mazu's citizens from the bottom of their hearts. They use various actions and channels to establish multiple connections with Mazu. They are active people and a major power in the social network centered on Mazu belief, who form an important bond, and contribute to the promotion of the development of Mazu belief and the stable development of the circle of Mazu belief.

"James W. Carey* once pointed out very wisely that 'authenticity' is continuously adapted and reconstructed to adapt to humans' goals, including the transformation of humanity himself. But science is not a set of privileged and basic reappearances, science is just part of our cultural exchanges."(James. 2005) "Chen Jinguo† also pointed out that modern people have no reason and qualifications, bringing with dogmatic thinking and God's vision, continuously showing the unwarranted pride of criticizing the wisdom and taste of the ancient Chinese and the common people in understanding the world, although the poetic wisdom of the common people is full of surprises and schemes."(Chen. 2005) The interaction of these sacrificial rituals as symbolic signs has effectively promoted the identity within the ethnic group and promoted the development of human society. Moreover, it will still play an important and active role in a certain period and within a certain range in the future.

The ceremony of Mazu Festival is a large-scale activity of collective mobilization, through a certain ceremony to convey and promote the ritual experience of interactive sense between humans and gods. Concepts and experiences are mostly internal and abstract conscious activities, which must be manifested through external physical actions and language forms. Under the long-term inheritance and cohesion, these behaviors have inevitably formed a procedural, standardized and institutionalized etiquette system, which can reflect the communication network of activities between Mazu in various places, Mazu and believers, believers and believers.

The ceremony of Mazu Festival is the main body of Mazu belief. It closely links people and gods through symbolic rituals. People express their prayers and reliance on gods. Mazu transmits the universality protection and relief to all living beings, strengthen the religious emotions that can be shared by each other. People can receive and feel the sacred atmosphere of Mazu, hope to receive Mazu's help or inspiration in the process of ritual procedures, enhance the energy of life's existence, solve difficulties and avoid disasters, and bring prosperity to life and family. The ceremony of Mazu Festival takes the inheritance of offering incense as the core. It uses the ritual behavior of humans to god to obtain the protection and rescue of god to humans. God and humans are active objects of constantly interactive sense. Mazu's spiritual grace is prominent, and people's

* American famous scholars.

† The researcher of the Institute of World Religions, Chinese Academy of Social Sciences, and now he is the deputy director of the Institute of Contemporary Religions.

thanks to Mazu's grace has caused the temple to flourish and Mazu's efficacies spread far and widely, this produces a lively and close landscape of temple fair.

This kind of ritual with efficacious interaction as the main body is not superstition, it is self-selection after people have established their self-identity. It is the reintegration and re-creation of people's spiritual activities. It assembles the essence of traditional inspiration and culture. Through holding the ritual activities, it can exert the belief function of uniting social groups, build people's identity with Mazu culture and self-identity. It actively attaches to the social network system of the circle of Mazu belief, expresses common aspirations through group activities. (Peng, 2012)

1.3 The important nodes and influences in the ceremony of Mazu Festival

The ceremony of Mazu Festival includes the performances on Tianhou Square and cruising across the entire Meizhou Island.

The cruising across the entire Meizhou Island is purely public. During the cruising, some men carry the sedan chair that enshrines Mazu statue. It is equipped with a high-standard guard of honor, knocking the gongs. There are also performers on the team. The entire team is large and the scenery is spectacular and shocking. The route of the cruising is to connect the other 14 Mazu temples in Meizhou Island in series, closely link the "four pavilions[‡]" in Meizhou Island, and consider the relationship between each pavilion, to be fair, to ensure that everyone in Meizhou Island can be protect and blessed by Mazu. Mazu's cruising allows the public from all over the island to participate. When Mazu passes by, believers burn incense, worship, set off firecrackers, speaking words of the prayer in their mouths, looking forward to Mazu's blessing. The participants of the ceremony include all the people of Meizhou Island, and they constitute the protagonist of the ceremony.

Figure 2: Mazu's cruising

Source: Screenshot of video, taken by Ke Yihan, 2020

During the event, folklore teams from all over the world will bring various local folklore performances of intangible cultural heritage. At the same time, there will also be performances of Puxian opera, dragon-lion dances, cart-drums, walking on stilts and other folklore programs of Putian City. Many islanders who do business outland have rushed back to Meizhou Island to set up 23 love stations and volunteer service points along the route of Mazu cruising. They spontaneously purchase mineral water, cakes, beverages, etc., and distribute them to tourists from all over the world.

The participants, various links and content of the performance on Tianhou Square have been previously discussed above. The atmosphere of the performance is more serious and formal. It has political intent, and it intends to express the government's views and positions to Mazu believers at home and abroad and people from all walks of life, intending to make good use of Mazu belief, which is a folk belief, and fully playing the role and special significance of Mazu in the process of China's socialist harmonious society.

1.3.1 The chief worshiper

The chief worshiper of the ceremony for the 1060th anniversary of Mazu's birth in 2020 is Lin Jinzan, the chairman of the board of directors of Meizhou Mazu ancestral temple. The chief worshiper, as the representative of all believers, is elected by the folk people. As the closest person to Mazu, he stood in front of the altar, it appeared to be sacred and solemn, the important position is obvious. At the same time, he shoulders heavy trust, praying on behalf of all believers, people place all their hopes for a better life on him. His inner piety, his words and behaviors may directly affect Mazu's spirituality and sacredness. When holding the ceremony, everyone's eyes were focused on him. He is a representative of Mazu believers, and this is a status symbol. He is also the

[‡]This is the organizational form of the community in Meizhou Island in ancient society.

spokesperson of Mazu belief and has decision-making power when implementing various important matters related to Mazu. The chief worshiper, the chairman of the board of directors of Meizhou Mazu ancestral temple, is an elite of belief in Mazu belief and plays an important role in negotiating the development of Mazu belief and culture with the government. Therefore, his own degree of belief of Mazu belief and self-identity is crucial to the development of Mazu belief.

Figure 3: The chief worshiper, Lin Jinzan

Source: Screenshot of video, taken by Ke Yihan, 2020

1.3.2 The main worshipers

The main worshipers are Lin Zhaoshu, former Chairman of the All-China Federation of Overseas Chinese, Vice Chairman of the First and Second Session of the Chinese Mazu Cultural Exchange Association. Liu Jianyang, Secretary of the Putian Municipal Party Committee of the Communist Party of China. Li Jianhui, Mayor of Putian Municipal People's Government. Ruan Jun, Director of the Standing Committee of Putian Municipal People's Congress. Zhou Qingsong, Putian City CPPCC Chairman. Wu Guifang, Putian Municipal Committee Standing Committee Member, Publicity Department Director. Shen Bolin, Putian Municipal Committee Standing Committee Member. Shen Mengya, Secretary-General Putian Municipal People's Congress Standing Committee Deputy Director. Chen Huiqian, Putian City Deputy Mayor. Peng Lijing, Putian City CPPCC Vice Chairman, Yu Jianzhong, Executive Vice President of the Chinese Mazu Cultural Exchange, etc. They presented flower baskets to Mazu together and bowed three times to Mazu. The first bow, wishing the elements were propitious, the country prospered and the people enjoyed peace. The second bow, wishing there will be no disasters in four seasons, and there will be good things in an entire year. The three bows, wishing the prosperity of China and the safety and peace of the world.

Figure 4: The main worshipers

Source: Screenshot of video, taken by Ke Yihan, 2020

The main worshipers are basically composed of officials from government departments, they symbolize the official attitude and policy direction towards Mazu belief. Because the chief officials of cities often change, some of them may do not know Mazu at first. With the contact of work and the understanding of Mazu, they

began to gradually establish the identity of Mazu culture. From the perspective of work's needs and personal emotions, they have produced heartfelt respect for Mazu belief, which is the awakening of self-consciousness.

As a local business card of Putian City, Mazu is the most important cultural symbol for the development of tourism in Meizhou Island. The identity and affirmation of Mazu by local officials is an important measure to promote and introduce Mazu belief and Mazu culture to the outside world and the rest of the world. It is conducive to the formation of the social atmosphere of Mazu belief, and it is beneficial to promote the rapid development of Mazu belief with the help of official power and authority.

The composition of the chief worshiper and the main worshipers also verifies the model of Mazu belief jointly constructed by officials and the folk from another perspective. The folk elites act as the protagonists and lead the masses of believers in common belief. The official acts as an auxiliary force to guide the correct political direction and the development path, which can give full help in organizing large-scale activities, funds, and personnel. This model not only avoids the government's excessive intervention in folk beliefs, which may arouse the disgust and worry of the general believers, and enables the folk beliefs to meet the general needs of the general believers. At the same time, it can also use the form of civil organizations to bring civil elites and other social forces to gather together, allow Mazu to adapt to the new needs of the current state and social development, to carry out functional changes opportunely, and to guide a good social atmosphere. The status of folk elites is often inseparable from official support and recognition. They can better understand the official intentions. In the various activities and development of Mazu belief, they adhere to the national policies as important guidelines, abide by the law, and abide by various rules and regulations, from self-acceptance to influencing others, form a consensus, then form a series of stable social relationship, and promote the harmonious development of society.

1.3.3 The performers

As the most influential and largest ceremony of Mazu Festival, there were 456 performers in the ceremony, including singers and dancers, etc. The main personnel of the performance are students from Putian University, local residents of Meizhou Island mainly participate in knocking gongs and drums performances and carrying the sedan chairs. During the grand festivals of Mazu, local residents always put everything away and participate in Mazu's festivals wholeheartedly, especially middle-aged and elderly women. In recent years, under the promotion of the government and the drive of their parents, the believers of Mazu tend to be younger, more young people are also willing to participate in Mazu's folk activities and dedicate their efforts. This is also a manifestation of their identity of Mazu belief.

After young people learn about Mazu belief through various channels, they sublimate to their inner emotional identity, and finally give actual belief actions. The participation of students of Putian University is objectively an act of integration of social resources. Putian University is an important base for the study of Mazu culture. It opens special Mazu classes to teach Mazu culture systematically and scientifically. As a university, it can organize large-scale performances. When the Board of Directors of Mazu temple negotiated with Putian University to allow students to participate in the performance of Mazu Festival, Putian University's emphasis on Mazu belief and Mazu culture played a key role. Due to Putian University has an official background, everything is easier to communicate, the leaders and students also are proud to be able to participate in important activities of Mazu Festival.

Therefore, Putian University does its utmost to support Mazu's various activities. Meanwhile, all aspects of the activities can also form a good record and be better preserved, so that scholars from all walks of life can better conduct research on Mazu. As a voluntary job, the students of Putian University participated voluntarily. The performance rehearsal cycle was long, and it has a long way from the University to Meizhou Island, it needs to spend one hour on the way by car. But they did not hesitate to take up the study time to do these meaningful things. For students, it is a brand-new experience, which is an improvement of self-emotion and cognitive level. After students come into contact with Mazu, they unconsciously join the team to promote Mazu culture. They are excited to tell their experience to friends, parents, classmates. In future study and life, they can study harder, consciously abide by the University's disciplines, and use Mazu spirit to guide their ways forward.

Local residents of Meizhou Island also play the role of performers in the ceremonies. In addition to participating in activities and performances, in the environment where they live, for foreign tourists, local residents are also performers. During the ceremony, lanterns and festoons were hanging everywhere on Meizhou Island, creating a very good festive environment and atmosphere. The Management Committee of Meizhou Island also organizes various folk festivals, such as the collection of Mazu cultural works, large-scale creations and paintings of Mazu culture, and organizing hundreds of national photographers entering Meizhou Island. These festivals enhance social interaction, and greatly enriching the daily life of local residents, allowing them to relax and entertain in their work and daily life.

This is a very good inheritance of Mazu culture, which can mobilize the participation of residents and help them better understand and identify with Mazu culture. The ceremony of Mazu Festival is not only a sacrifice ritual to worship Mazu, but also a folk carnival for self-entertainment. It has a strong appeal and local characteristics, and is loved by the residents of the community. The involvement and emotional attachment of

the residents can be perceived by others in terms of the voice and expression of dialogue with them, and self-awareness has become an important source of subjective perception.

The contemporary ceremony of Mazu Festival has been carefully planned and designed, such as the selection of the host and the participation of students from Putian University. These are all to make the effect of the ceremony present a certain sense of beauty. Skilled performance, uniform costumes, and shocking scenes can strongly grasp the audience's hearts and arouse strong resonance, which is what the organizer wants to see. But it also makes it impossible for performers to fully appreciate the natural mood swings that immerse themselves in.

Certainly, this has a certain difference from the initial sacrificial activities. The initial sacrificial activities were pure to express their reliance on and respect for Mazu. Every household of the local residents had the opportunity to participate in sacrificial activities. It is also a kind of honor when seeing their own family members appearing in sacrificial activities and assuming some duties. This kind of emotion will give the interaction of the traditional sacrificial ritual into a sense and value of self-satisfaction and self-realization. This special meaning will make residents extremely invested and prone to emotional fluctuations.

Such emotional fluctuations will also be passed on to the performers, which will further stimulate their desires to perform and make them engage in performance with their self-emotions. Due to changes in actual needs, regardless of the purpose, the ceremony will convey to people a positive and up-to-date culture that is shared by the whole people. Multiple interactions can form the Chinese identity of Mazu culture. "On the overall level of a community, the villagers have a sense of being a member of the whole by participating in the ritual, they have found their roles positioning and mutual relationship in the process of symbolic interaction." (Zeng, 2013) Through this, they have completed the psychological construction of the group's sense of belonging, formed the identity of the group and other members, and also established the identity of themselves. They will inevitably express this sense of pride and identity through sharing videos, pictures, chats and other ways to their friends, classmates, and parents, etc. This will add potential nodes and weak connection relationships to build the social network of Mazu belief. Through individual networks convey effective, correct and intuitive information about Mazu Festival and Mazu culture.

1.3.4 The audiences

The audiences in the ceremony of Mazu Festival refer to the local residents who participated in the scene, tourists from other places, and netizens who watched the ceremonial activities through live webcasts.

In 2020, due to the worldwide spread of the COVID-19, no guests and overseas Chinese at home and abroad were invited to observe the ceremony of Mazu Festival, there had not been a lively scene of crowds as the same as in the past, but the ceremony of Mazu Festival was still held, following the principle of reducing the scale but not reducing the specifications, reducing the procedures but not reducing the inheritance, and reducing the intensity of publicity but not reducing the intensity of epidemic prevention and control. It is different from previous Mazu Festivals, this year increased the part of online interaction. The ceremony was broadcast simultaneously through CCTV News, CCTV, Xinhua Live Cloud, Toutiao, Baidu, Sina, Youku, E-Live, and the official live broadcast platform of Meizhou Mazu ancestral temple and other platforms. All of the worldwide Mazu believers can worship and respect Mazu through the online video, and jointly pray the blessing for the victory over the COVID-19 and the sharing of peace.

The usual number of people participating in the ceremonies of Mazu Festival is limited, most people can only watch the ceremonies through computers, TV or mobile phone. "At the ceremony's site, people will consciously show their actions, both as the audience and as part of the performance. Just like many documentaries and many painters, they turn something that is originally not a performance into a performance." (Liu, 2018) For example, the audiences' behaviors of taking photographs, gaze, folding hands and so on often affect each other, forming a strong atmosphere of presence sense. The sense of sacredness, participation, and interactive experience at the scene is relatively strong. The sacrificial ceremony pays great attention to the restoration of traditions and innovations in music and dance, costumes, sacrificial vessels, and tedious etiquette, to establish a sacred cultural space. The space in front of the electronic screen cannot force the audiences to abide by the same etiquette rules as on site, and maintain a pious and solemn emotion and state. Because the space in front of the screen is an unstable spatial environment, the audience can be distracted, laugh and even leave the scene at will. However, modern media methods can display the ceremonies from multiple angles, take close-ups of the overall environment and layout from multiple angles. The overall visual effect is better. It allows concrete images to enter the audience's hearts, rather than letting abstract concepts stay in the audience's minds. During the important festivals of Mazu, there are always many devout believers and tourists who travel far to Meizhou Island to worship Mazu, experience Mazu culture, and participate in Mazu celebrations. They regard themselves as Mazu's family members, and Mazu's festival is regarded as family affairs and the most important thing. Participating in that is not only due to responsibilities and obligations, but also a self-identity and lofty belief in Mazu.

In 2020, the ceremony of Mazu Festival attracted many Chinese and overseas Chinese at home and abroad to observe the grand ceremony. Representatives of Mazu cultural institutions in the United States, Spain, Japan,

Australia, Malaysia, Singapore, Canada and other countries and regions also used online video to connect 'clouds' to worship Mazu, expressing the common desire of carrying forward Mazu spirit, helping each other, working together to defeat the COVID-19. At the same time, they also organized corresponding folklore activities to worship Mazu and passed them to the organizers through online video. These materials would be preserved well and become precious memories. These activities reflect people's devotion and emphasis on Mazu belief. The rituals are collective memories and become a special symbol with the development of history, and form the rules that people follow together. When important festivals, there is no need to force the believers, they will consciously put aside their work and participate in the activities. This is an important manifestation of self-identity of Chinese people to Mazu belief.

Meanwhile, people who watch the ceremonial performance, will generate some emotional feedback based on the on-site performance activities and actions. It is to be known that Chinese people are used to building their own social networks with self-centeredness. This kind of emotional feedback and information implantation not only easily affects the individual's own social network, but also transmits it to the surrounding environment and individuals through contact with the surrounding people. According to social network theory, the influence of this kind of communication can spread within the 'three degrees', that is, it will have an impact on friends, friends' friends, and friends of friends' friends.

The ceremony of Mazu Festival is divided into two parts, inside the venue and outside the venue. The inside venue can be called official sacrifice. The performance is performed under the rules and process, which characterizes the style and characteristics of ancient official performances. But the number of audiences is limited and there is no interaction with the audience. The outside venue is the folklore performance part of the sacrificial ceremony, including folklore performance teams from all over the country and local folklore of Putian City, as well as the most important Mazu's cruising and other activities. Local residents, tourists, and Mazu believers from all over the country can participate in the interaction and experience at a close distance, and the effect is good and strong. Although there is a large number of people participated in the activities, under the organization and coordination of the Board of Directors of Mazu ancestral temple, the activities were carried out in a peaceful and lively atmosphere. People reaped the joy of participating in the activities and took photos to share with friends from time to time, or sharing videos, photos or words to instant social network platforms, such as WeChat Moments and Douyin, such this they can spread and influence the latest information to a personal social network.

1.4 The interactive relationships in the community reflected in the ceremony of Mazu Festival

The relationship between people in the ceremony of Mazu Festival is also an important aspect of investigating the identity of a community and an ethnic group. Mazu temples and organizations around the world also highlight the social network relationship extended by the relationship between humans and gods.

"Religious belief is a sublimation of social relationship and a transcending form of social relationship." (Georg; Cao. 2003) The ceremonial ceremonies all have a part that the chief worshiper reads the sacrificial text. Its symbolic meaning is to show to all believers that we all use the same way to express worship to the gods and ancestors, follow the same moral and social norms. Therefore, every individual can have this kind of self-identity. We all are Mazu people, we all are Chinese, and we all have the same ancestor. In this way, the relationship between humans and gods has been extended to the relationship between people.

The ceremony of Mazu Festival is the greatest and grand event of Mazu folklore. It has the largest scale. In particular, Mazu's cruising around Meizhou Island was almost entirely attended by all the local residents. Various villages and the 15 Mazu temples on the island cooperated, established a good network of friendships and formed a close interactive relationship.

Fei Xiaotong[§] uses the concept of 'the structure of grade' to express the close or alienated relationship between people in traditional society. In a sense, this also confirms the structure of a social relationship that the status difference exists between people in the ethnic groups. The members of the society are different due to their status and identities. In the historical development and inheritance, it has formed a whole set of rules, regulations and moral norms. As long as different people strictly abide by different etiquette, they can get what they want, and society will be stable and prosperous. This kind of etiquette is an abstraction of social hierarchy and ethical order, or a symbolic sign.

Everyone in the ceremony of Mazu Festival must know their identity and exercise different etiquette. The roles and relationships of people in ceremonies can also be seen as a kind of symbol, which metaphors and symbolizes the role played by the individuals in the group and the social relationship with others. The folk belief elites play an important role in the ceremony. They are usually responsible for leading, planning, organizing, determining the scale of the ceremony, who will be assigned to be organizer, how to arrange the funding, etc. This also reflects their positions in the social network. The positions are the affirmation of their identity.

[§]Famous Sociologist, Anthropologist, Ethnologist, social activist, one of the founders of Chinese Sociology and Anthropology.

With the development of the times, in Meizhou Island, most of the believers who actively participated in the activities were women, whether it was to worship ancestors or Mazu. This lack of women's right to speak is formed under the long-term traditional society and cultural background. Due to the need for taking care of the family, women generally stay at home, thus forming the traditional thinking that male is in charge of the outside things and female is in charge of the inside things. Therefore, a specific social atmosphere has been formed. During the ceremony, they prepared sacrificial offerings, burned incense, bowed down worshipping, and read blessing words in mouth, without any taboo. Although women have become the main part of participants in sacrificial activities, men still occupy a dominant position in the organization of sacrificial activities, playing the role of organization and leader. This can be judged from the gender composition of the board members of Meizhou Mazu ancestral temple. Currently, there are only 3 women among the 30 board members.

The power struggles, the possession of knowledge, and the difference between men and women in the ceremony can all find their corresponding prototypes in the actual social relationship structure. In other words, the relationship and role positioning between gods and humans in the ceremony of Mazu Festival are just symbolic repetitions of the relationship and role positioning between people in real life. Etiquette as a ritual is the confirmation and practice of the social rules established by society. People who participate in it have found their own role positioning and mutual relationship in the process of symbolic interaction, completed self-identity of the group, self and other members, and on this basis, the corresponding social network relationship has been formed. In this relationship, people remain in their proper sphere, society has been integrated, developed and continued. (Meng; Shuai. 2016)

Summary

The ceremony of Mazu Festival most obviously and intensively reflects and expresses people's current understanding, interpretation and views of Mazu belief, and explains the relationship between Mazu culture and social life, social rules, operational norms and order. At present, people regard the ceremony of Mazu Festival as a location for emotional expression. People are surrounded by the atmosphere of Mazu belief, remove all burdens and precautions, and their souls are sublimated. The ceremony of Mazu Festival is like a performance stage. At this stage, the individuals, groups and society form a close interactive relationship. The ceremony of Mazu Festival is also a process of communication between humans and the sacred power. People regard the ceremony of Mazu Festival as a way of communication, but it is not only the communication between humans and gods. To a certain extent, there is also a process of communication between people participating in the ceremony, including body communication and language communication, etc.

Fundamentally speaking, the communication between humans and gods and the communication between people can be attributed to the symbolic interaction between individuals and society. In this interactive relationship, people have constructed a meaningful way of life, an independent self-identity, a broad and stable social network. This kind of meaning system permeates the daily life of families and regions. The daily life of families and local residents are infiltrated and supported by this paradigm of meaning. The older generations discuss the situational experience that they share through this paradigm of meaning. In the process of socialization, especially within the scope of family, community, and country, this meaning system is constantly being reproduced and constitutes the basic framework of imagination. Through this framework, people get closer to their social experience and gain a certain label of personal identity, people can find the organization, and integrate into it. In the connection of specific organizers, a stable social network centered on Mazu belief is formed, which is of great significance to promoting internal unity, maintaining social order, promoting social development, and enhancing the cohesion of the Chinese nation.

Research Objectives

- 1 To study the important nodes and their influence of the social network in Mazu Festival.
- 2 To analyze the interactive relationships in the community reflected in the ceremony of Mazu Festival.

Methodology

This article adopts the method of qualitative research, consults a large number of historical documents and materials, and fully grasps the important content such as the organizers, ritual process, and constituent elements of the ceremony of Mazu Festival.

Through field work, the author have mastered the first-hand information and data of the ceremonies of Mazu Festival in 2020 and 2021, and recorded the important feelings of the participants, audiences, actor, researchers and organizers of the ceremony through on-site interviews, and formed the important research basis of Chinese people constructing their social network. At the same time, using modern networks and new media technologies, such as photography and recording equipment, to record and save a large number of important materials.

Conclusion

Mazu Festival is the world's intangible cultural heritage and an important traditional custom in China for thousands of years with profound connotations. The ceremony process of Mazu Festival reflects the organization and execution of the entire event, and builds an important social network relationship. Each node connects and interacts with Mazu belief in their own way through their respective locations, and uses their own social resources to play a role for developing Mazu belief. In modern society, Mazu Festival is more conducive to uniting Chinese people all over the world, keeping close contact, strengthening national cohesion, and promoting the prosperity and development of Mazu belief.

Discovery of this article

Mazu Festival has high research value. In modern society, the ceremony of Mazu Festival not only has strong historical, cultural and artistic value, but also has high ornamental value. Mazu Festival is an important link between individuals, organizations and Mazu belief. By sorting out the ceremony process of Mazu Festival, researching and analyzing the relationship of social network in the Mazu Festival will help people to connect more closely with the Mazu organizations, give play to the advantages of social resources, and use the role of the network to spread Mazu culture more effectively. This will help enhance cohesion and better develop Mazu culture.

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